

DETERMINATION OF MICROBIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS, ALGAL BIOTOXINS AND TRACE ELEMENTS IN OYSTERS FROM A MEDITERRANEAN LAGOON

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Pacific oysters (*Crassostrea gigas*) are highly nutritious bivalves representing an important dietary constituent. Due to the growing need for aquaculture differentiation, the interest is increasing in Italian oyster farming. This will require the classification of new productive areas in both coastal lagoons and open waters. The objective of the present investigation was to assess the presence of 16 trace elements (Al, As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Mo, Ni, Pb, Rb, Se, Sn, V, Zn), biotoxins (PSTs, LTs -OA, DTXs, YTXs and AZAs, DA), *V. parahaemolyticus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* spp. in *C. gigas* from an experimental pilot farm set up in the Calich Lagoon (Sardinia, Italy) in the frame of the EU Interreg program RETRALAGS. Samples of *C. gigas* were collected in winter, spring, summer and autumn of 2019. The EU legal limits for Cd and Pb were never exceeded, the farmed oysters were safe to consumers. The results pointed out a high significant seasonal variation of Cd, Mn, Ni, and V. The highest values were found for Fe and Al in autumn, for Zn in winter and spring. *E. coli* was always present overlapping the EU limits of 230 MPN/100g. *Salmonella* spp. was never detected, and *V. parahaemolyticus* was detected only in summer samples. The potentially toxic microalga *Dinophysis acuminata* was found in the lagoon water without accumulation of biotoxins. Pacific oysters were confirmed as suitable bioindicators of the health status of coastal lagoons. Concentrations of trace elements and microbiological parameters were highly affected by season of collection.

Keywords: mediterranean lagoon, food safety, shellfish, trace elements, biotoxins, bacteria.